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**THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE
MANAGEMENT OF THE BANKING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN**

Mardiyev Bunyod

Tashkent State University of Economics

Assistant of the Department of Innovation Management

bunyodmardiyev7095@gmail.com

Togonov Ibrohimkhoja

International School of Finance

Technology and Science

Management department assistant

togonovibrohimxoja8@gmail.com

Abstract: The article discusses the improvement of the effectiveness of measures aimed at improving banking activities in the territory of Uzbekistan and the stabilisation of the national economy with the help of digitalisation of the sector. Also, based on the capabilities of our country, the practical application of the standards of the world financial system will be considered.

Keywords: digitisation, banking activity, national economy, integration, credit, system, entrepreneurship, innovative management, central bank.

Introduction: The importance of the banking system in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is incomparable. Currently, computer technologies and artificial intelligence are being actively introduced into various sectors of the economy, including the banking system. This technology is something new in modernizing banking services, handling losses, enabling migration and improving efficiency.

This program is also an important profession in bank transformation. The Presidential Decree "On Measures for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies" adopted in March 2021 determined the main directions of the development of the country's economy and the bank's artificial intelligence technologies.

Japan's Waseda University Digital Government Institute in collaboration with the International CIO Academy (IAC) has announced the 2023 18th Waseda World Digital Government Rankings Survey. This study identifies digital transformation in 66 countries/economies with advanced digital

technologies¹. The 2023 rankings show significant growth trends in the use of digital technologies, such as generative artificial intelligence, in government activities. These technologies are expected to continue to develop further in the coming years. The difference between this survey and previous surveys is that this year there was a change in the number of target countries, that is, they added four countries, including Uzbekistan, to this list.

Table 1.

2023 18th Waseda University World Digital Government Comprehensive Ranking²

#	Country	Total	23	Italy	76.3371	46	Portugal	64.5839
1	Denmark	93.2902	24	Iceland	76.2060	47	Brunei	64.4795
2	Canada	92.2459	25	Indonesia	75.9850	48	Kenya	63.9137
3	England	91.9278	26	Spain	74.7971	49	Columbia	63.8306
4	New Zealand	91.4979	27	Austria	74.3202	50	Mexico	62.8448
5	Singapore	91.3919	28	Belgium	73.9079	51	Egypt	62.1200
6	South Korea	89.6937	29	Malaysia	73.7182	52	Romania	61.6217
7	USA	88.7400	30	India	73.0972	53	Argentina	60.5759
8	Netherlands	85.8224	31	Hong Kong	72.8246	54	Brazil	60.4387
9	Estonia	85.4313	32	Kazakhstan	72.6281	55	Bahrain	60.1645
10	Ireland	83.9196	33	Oman	72.6097	56	Bangladesh	58.7585
11	Japan	83.5541	34	South Africa	70.0274	57	Uzbekistan	58.2306
12	Germany	83.4543	35	Russia	69.4431	58	Morocco	57.5710
13	Norway	81.6249	36	Philippines	68.6910	59	Nigeria	56.9814
14	Sweden	81.4611	37	Israel	68.1137	60	Peru	56.4251
15	Taiwan	80.6658	38	Czech	67.8147	61	Tunisia	53.5153
16	Switzerland	80.5450	39	Lithuania	67.7550	62	Pakistan	50.2313
17	Australia	80.3236	40	Chile	67.0599	63	Paraguay	49.8242
18	Finland	79.9412	41	Poland	67.0386	64	Fiji	48.0853
19	Thailand	79.0126	42	Turkey	66.9790	65	Costa Rica	47.6883
20	Saudi Arabia	78.9733	43	China	65.3063	66	Ghana	41.8802
21	UAE	78.9536	44	Uruguay	65.1550			
22	France	77.1086	45	Vietnam	64.5990			

From Table 1, we can see that our country has risen to 57th place out of 66 digitized governments. It follows from this that the work being done in our country to digitize industries and increase transparency is not in vain.

In particular, it is the financial vein of the State "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2020-2025", to ensure the implementation of the "Strategy of Development" and to further improve and reform the activities of banks the signing of the decree also determined the importance of the topic.

In addition, paragraph 99 of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, which is the main program and main strategy of our country, sets goals such as "further automation of the process of ensuring the security of the state border using artificial intelligence technologies." This means strengthening not only borders but also our financial and economic security with the help of digital and artificial intelligence.

¹ 18th Waseda -IAC World Digital Government Ranking 2023. November 2023

² <https://iacio.org/>

Over the past decade, since the beginning of the financial technology revolution, the financial services industry has witnessed the emergence of hundreds of individual digital banks around the world. These banks have revolutionized the way digitally savvy consumers save, borrow, transact and invest.

1- Picture. Dynamics of funds received on bank cards and their cashing volumes³

It can be seen from Figure 1 that in January-September of this year, the amount of funds transferred to bank cards amounted to 740 trillion soums and increased by 1.3 times compared to the corresponding period of 2023. During this period, the owners of bank cards cashed 167 trillion soums on their cards, of which 140 trillion soums were withdrawn through ATMs.

The share of cashing out of funds received on bank cards is decreasing year by year. Specifically, this indicator:

- 27.4 percent in 2022;
- 24.4 percent in 2023;
- In 2024, it was 22.6 percent.

These statistics inform us that the process of digitization in our country is progressing rapidly. Digitization in almost all areas of the country is evidence of a transition to electronic payment systems.

TABInsights is evaluating the performance of more than 150 leading digital banks worldwide from 2021 and ranking them based on a balanced scorecard. This scorecard assesses banks' performance across five key dimensions: customers, market/product coverage, profitability, asset and deposit growth, and funding. Size and volume will not be the main factors; rather, factors such as *profitability*, *operational efficiency*, *ability to secure funding*, and *how these digital banks maintain a strong loan book and balance sheet* are considered⁴.

³ <https://cbu.uz/>

⁴ <https://tabinsights.com/>

The assessment included more than 150 leading participants across 39 markets and was conducted to identify the Top 100 Digital Banks worldwide. The top 100 list is divided into different regions: 41 from the Asia-Pacific region, 38 from Europe, 10 from North America, five from South America, and three each from the Middle East and Africa. Unfortunately, there are no banks of ours in this list of banks, not only of our country but also of Central Asia. The list is being started by China's **WeBank** bank.

The modern, constantly changing technological environment forces all economic units to undergo digital transformation. Digital transformation has a dual function, as it allows banking organizations to offer new service channels through new electronic platforms (e-banking, virtual banking) and service points (e-stores, POS), as well as reduces their operating costs by limiting their number. This is why the banking industry worldwide spends three times more on IT investment than any other industry overall, compared to physical stores and the employees they employ. Business models are under control in the banking industry. Digitization, disruptive innovation and new technologies are changing traditional business models and processes. As a result, banks must change their business models to interact with customers, manage middle and back-office operations, and be competitive and future-proof. Therefore, digital transformation is defined as "a process aimed at improving unity by making significant changes in its structure by combining information, information technology, communication and connectivity technologies." Digital transformation includes a broad understanding of banking activities, in particular: the digitization of documents, electronic signatures for transactions, e-learning, teleconferencing, online trading platforms, digital stores, electronic calculations and payments. Customers are increasingly using digital disruption and new types of solutions are emerging in this sector. Thus, new business models in the banking sector are essential to focus on all important banking processes. The transition to electronic banking is nevertheless the result of other equally important factors, including the need for banks to adapt to the new technological information of the time. is to offer an additional service channel, deregulate the banking market and allow other companies (eg Alipay, Paypal) to enter to increase competition. Ref used the term "open banking point" to describe all non-banking companies that offer banking-like products and services. In their research, half of the population was ready to use such products. Most people now do their banking on their computer or mobile phone. The abundance of possibilities, as well as the time and cost savings and the ease of use of these applications, give them a constant share of traditional banking channels (bank branches). Also, through these applications, owners-clients will be able to receive information through digital media about the real-time evaluation of investment products, bank reward programs and expenses incurred to have a more favourable tax regime. The advantages mentioned above make mobile banking more attractive not only for young people but also for all smartphone owners. For the same reasons, Ref uses the term "digital natives" to describe those born after 1980 who are familiar with and receptive to new electronic technologies. Therefore, the Greek banking administration is investing significantly in electronic banking infrastructure, which is expected to depreciate very quickly due to the level of adoption of these technologies by bank customers and the savings of resources by limiting traditional banking activities. The penetration of electronic means of banking transactions is part of the banking culture today. Of course, there are those who disagree. According to them, the reduction of brick-and-mortar bank branches and the adoption of digital alternatives, even if they reduce costs, are not profitable. By studying the effectiveness of IT service channels, they concluded that when bank branches are closed, opportunities to increase revenues as well as costs are lost. In any case, digital banking provides access to banking services to people in underdeveloped areas, as no investment or infrastructure is required from banks. According to other economists, digitization of banking will bring many benefits to organizations (banking institutions) and their customers. Banks using digital technologies are able to save time, reduce operational costs and optimize methods of monitoring, risk management and control, as well as offer quality products and services in the market. Customers using

digital banking can reduce the time between transactions and complete them securely. People living in remote areas will be able to use banking services without the physical presence of banks; competitive differentiation, stores and services operate with fewer employees, reduce operating costs and standardize internal processes⁵.

Today, the banks of our Republic are abandoning the seal and traditional signature. The main reason for this is convenience for customers and remote work.

The management structure developed by the bank in increasing the efficiency of work, creating a good communication environment between the manager and the employee, encouraging, and providing social and material support is a lever that determines the path of its future potential. In many countries of the world, the following methods are used to improve the activity of banks:

- ✓ Innovative management system
- ✓ Full transfer of documentation issues to online mode and wide use of electronic signature
- ✓ Conduct continuous control over the qualifications and potential of employees
- ✓ Interval rotation of sections to prevent stagnation
- ✓ Application of competitiveness and advantage aspects, in particular, the relative reduction of transfer commission prices and ease of payments
- ✓ Improving the CRM (Customer Relationship Management) system.

Technology and innovation. In banks, which are the main link of the financial market, computers, machines that perform money transfers and operations, and mobile communication tools that create a good communication environment with customers, all of these are important criteria in banking activity. Enrichment of financial services with Blockchain, Cloud banking system, powerful and extensive Big Data (Hadoop, Apache Spark, Apache Kafka, MongoDB, Cassandra), platforms and technologies of neobanks will further ensure the prospects of banks in our country.

Security system. Security is the most important factor in attracting large-scale investors. The reason is that the depositor should be able to see the security of his money. At a time when many of the world's banks are victims of cyber-attacks, a high level of bank security system gives a competitive advantage. SAP, CGI Open Finance, Oracle FLEXCUBE, Temenos Transact - Core Banking, TCS BaNCS, Validis, Symphony, Mambu, Avaloq Banking Suite, and Q2ebanking are mentioned as the best systems of 2022 currently used in the bank. The ATM (Automatic Teller Machines) security system is the most popular as it has several conveniences.

The role of banks in the economy can be explained by the allocation of investment loans. This concept, which first appeared in the form of in-kind, creates wide opportunities as "credit" in its modern interpretation. It has been performing several tasks such as integration of industries and networks, support of entrepreneurs, financing of projects and so on.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of the digital transformation of banks, the emergence of modern banking services and new payment methods, as well as the emergence of different ways of communication between customers and the bank, especially accelerates the communication between the bank and the customer. Digital modernization of the economy is one of the most popular issues today. In the context of the development of world economic relations, the integration of the economy of individual countries and the development of payment systems, in particular, the development of non-cash forms of payment, and types of digital services of banks, is observed. As a result of the ongoing reforms, market mechanisms for providing services are being introduced in the banking system, their types are expanding, and financial openness is increasing for entrepreneurs and citizens.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10804843>

In addition to increasing the potential of banks and ensuring their positive position in the economy, first of all, introducing new methods to their internal structure reforms, and then step-by-step monetary transactions, time-payment loans, solving documentation processes in favour of customers and promoting orderly money circulation. must be provided. This will improve the situation of problematic situations related to banks in the territory of the country, and the immunity of trust will be formed in people. Of course, the state takes the leading role in ensuring mutual control of the economy and the financial system, its price policy, foreign economic relations, customs services, export-import processes, and exchange rate changes also affect the activity of commercial banks. will not pass. To achieve change, stabilization and growth in one area, it is necessary to ensure strict supervision of other sectors and areas.

The experience of countries that have already developed the banking and financial system plays a special role in the development model of our republic. After all, the unique economic potential is an important factor for the country to be called "developed", therefore, the practical implementation of the banking and financial system of an economically superior country will firmly determine the development path of our country. Through this policy, it is possible to increase the share of banks in GDP.

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